

Examining Entrepreneurial Intention and Propensity to Main Types of Entrepreneurship in Terms of Gender Variable

Umut Ahmet SEYREK^{1*}, Kürşat DEMİRYÜREK², Nur İlkey ABACI³

Ondokuz Mayıs University, Institute of Graduate Studies, Department of Entrepreneurship and Innovation, Samsun

¹<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3274-5894>

²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6193-9957>

³<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4411-2800>

¹22281409@stu.omu.edu.tr

²kursatd@omu.edu.tr

³ilkay.sonmez@omu.edu.tr

*Corresponding author : 22281409@stu.omu.edu.tr

Research article

Article History:

Received: 4 November 2026

Accept: 15 January 2026

Available online:

Keywords:

I- Entrepreneurial intention

II- Opportunity entrepreneurship

III- Creative entrepreneurship

IV- Gender difference

V- Faculty of agriculture

ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurial intention reflects an individual's desire for entrepreneurship and their potential to act accordingly. In this context, entrepreneurial intention is a key indicator in understanding an individual's decision-making process to become an entrepreneur. Furthermore, determining which type of entrepreneurship individuals are more likely to incline—opportunistic entrepreneurship and creative entrepreneurship—is crucial for understanding the dynamics of the entrepreneurial ecosystem, particularly in the agricultural sector. Considering the contraction in the agricultural sector and the sector's need for entrepreneurship, the aim of this research is to examine the entrepreneurial intentions of senior agricultural faculty students and their tendencies to these two basic entrepreneurship types, in terms of gender. By reaching a full sample size through the survey of students who had taken entrepreneurship courses within the research population, the data were analyzed descriptively and correlational. Of the 169 participants, 45% are undecided about their entrepreneurial intentions, while 53% of the same group are inclined to opportunistic entrepreneurship. When entrepreneurial intentions were examined by gender, female students are undecided, while male students are intentioned to entrepreneurship. An examination of students' propensity for two basic types of entrepreneurships by gender revealed that female students are significantly inclined to creative entrepreneurship, while males are significantly inclined to opportunistic entrepreneurship. These results are expected to provide a concrete and meaningful indicator for relevant literature, institutions, and the sector.

Giriřimcilik Niyetinin ve Temel Giriřimcilik Türüne Eğilimin Cinsiyet Deęiřkeni Açısından İncelenmesi

Arařtırma Makalesi

Makale Tarihiçesi:

Geliř tarihi:

Kabul tarihi:

Online yayınlanma:

Anahtar Kelimeler:

Giriřimcilik Niyeti

Fırsat Giriřimcilięi

Yaratıcı Giriřimcilik

Cinsiyet Farklılıęı

Ziraat Fakóltesi

Özet

Giriřimcilik niyeti, bireyin giriřimcilik isteęini ve bu doęrultuda eyleme geçme potansiyelini yansıtır. Bu bağlamda giriřimcilik niyeti, bireyin giriřimci olmak için karar verme sürecinin anlaşılmasında önemli bir göstergedir. Ayrıca, bireylerin giriřimcilik alan yazınında ele alınan iki temel giriřimcilik türü olan fırsat giriřimcilięi ve yaratıcı giriřimcilik arasında hangi türe daha yatkın olduklarının belirlenmesi, özellikle tarım sektöründe giriřimcilik ekosisteminin dinamiklerini anlamak açısından önem taşımaktadır. Bu doęrultuda arařtırmanın amacı, tarım sektöründe yaşanan daralma ve sektörün giriřimcilięe duyduęu ihtiyaç dikkate alınarak, ziraat fakóltesi son sınıf öęrencilerinin giriřimcilik niyetlerini ve iki temel giriřimcilik türüne yönelik eğilimlerini, cinsiyet deęiřkeni açısından incelemektir. Arařtırma evreni bünyesinde giriřimcilik dersi almıř öęrencilerin anket çalıřmasına tam katılımı ile tam örneklem sayısına erişilerek, veriler betimsel ve ilişkiyel yönlerden analiz edilmiştir. Toplamda 169 katılımcıdan %45'inin giriřimcilik niyeti açısından kararsız olduęu ve aynı grubun %53'ünün fırsat giriřimcilięine eğilimli olduęu bulunmuřtur. Giriřimcilik niyeti cinsiyete göre incelendięinde kadın öęrencilerin kararsız, erkek öęrencilerin ise giriřimcilięe niyetli olduęu bulunmuřtur. Öęrencilerin iki temel giriřimcilik türüne eğilim durumları cinsiyete göre incelendięinde kadın öęrencilerin anlamlı derecede yaratıcı giriřimcilięe eğilimli, erkeklerin ise fırsat giriřimcilięine eğilimli olduęu ortaya çıkmıřtır. Bu sonuçların ilgili literatüre, kurumlara ve sektöre anlamlı somut bir gösterge olması beklenmektedir.

Introduction

Since entrepreneurship essentially involves creating value, it has serious importance in numerous fields. And in this respect, it is a concept open to exploration through more in-depth and comprehensive research. In a scientific study covering five member countries representing the EU, it was seen that entrepreneurship has a significant mitigating effect against economic shocks and plays a serious role in diversifying the economy and innovation processes (Meyer and de Jongh, 2018). Entrepreneurship, which is fed by multiple sources, especially knowledge, is a shifting critical discipline that has a driving force for the development of the state by flowing into the macro economy through individual, group, organizational and social channels. van

Praag and Versloot (2007) stated that entrepreneurship contributes to the welfare of a country due to its features of reducing unemployment, increasing production and developing innovative products and services. Entrepreneurship has become an important research area that attracts the attention of all interested parties, from scientists to politicians, as it is seen as the best solution to the challenges of sustainable development according to the concrete results of its effects. The typical judgment seen in entrepreneurship concepts is to create value for society (Jones et al., 2020). What will ensure its continuity is the continuity of generations with entrepreneurial potential. We can view entrepreneurship as a growing, evolving, and prolific entity. At this point, as a scientific study points out, the increasing of the entrepreneurial population and the continuous infusion of new entrepreneurial candidates into the system by higher education institutions are a matter of economic security for a country as a whole (Manik and Sidharta, 2016). In fact, it has been emphasized that universities play a role in creating entrepreneurship by providing the necessary knowledge and skills for prospective entrepreneurs to establish their first businesses (Gorman et al., 1997). Within this transmitter and receiver relationship between the student and the university, knowing the intentions to become entrepreneur and tendencies to entrepreneurship types of students will be fundamental research fields for specific aims. It has been said that intention, which involves the cognitive process of directing beliefs, perceptions, and other external inputs into actual action, can best predict entrepreneurship, which is defined as a type of planned activity (Ajzen, 1991). A study on entrepreneurial intentions, which looks at the situation from the perspective of unemployment in India, highlights the need for university graduates to transform from job seekers to job creators (Anal and Singh, 2023). It was found that high correlation between higher education and entrepreneurial intention (Kolvereid and Moen, 1997). According to a study conducted among international students in Türkiye, students who have taken entrepreneurship courses are more willing to become entrepreneurs, and intention is a key factor in determining whether they want to become entrepreneurs (Usman and Yenita, 2019). Entrepreneurial intention is explained in the literature by processing different concepts such as creating a business concept, starting a business, designing a plan to solve the perceived problem by starting a business, belief in success and entrepreneurial career (Thompson, 2009; Chhabra et al., 2020; Anal and Singh, 2023). Entrepreneurial intention can be defined as the will to establish a new business or continue entrepreneurial action, which emerges from the internal motivation and consciousness triggered by individual benefit (Ngat and Tuyet, 2023). According to another definition, entrepreneurial intention is the main determinant of assertive behavior, which represents the planned and conscious effort of an individual to start a new venture (Chen et al. 2022). The

vitality of intention lies in uncovering the desire for new ventures (Soomro et al., 2019). While research on intention is the most intensely studied, it is a vibrant field that can change depending on time, place, facts, impacts, and the current climate. For example, by re-measuring the entrepreneurial intentions of newly graduated workers in one sector of a developing country after several economic cycles based on changing economic and political conditions and identifying critical issues affecting intention, determining intentions across different groups, comparing different regions and sectors, and many other combinations of research, an in-depth and original scientific field on intention can be created. A comprehensive literature review of scientific studies on student entrepreneurial intentions conducted globally between 1996 and 2024 demonstrates that extensive research has been conducted in this area (Xanthopoulou and Sahinidis, 2024). However, it is essential to broaden the scope of intentions to include diverse subcomponents and a more in-depth research on specific audience by specializing into specific professional fields. Literature reviews in this context have revealed that few studies have been conducted specifically on senior students of agricultural faculties and agriculture field. One of the main components of this research is to determine the entrepreneurial intentions of new graduates, namely senior students, by taking into account the industrial development of Samsun province, which is located in an important economic region in terms of agriculture in our developing country, and by taking into account the current technological and innovative activities in the field of agricultural entrepreneurship.

The other main component of this research is to assess the target audience's tendencies to the fundamental entrepreneurial types of opportunity and creative entrepreneurship and to reveal the relationship between these propensity with intention. On the other hand, the explicit aim is to identify gender differences in this model. Shinnar et al., (2012) found that gender is a determinant of entrepreneurial intention.

Many types of entrepreneurships have emerged from the past to the present in line with the needs and changes of age according to future expectations and predictions. Entrepreneurship varies in different regions, different economies and even within institutional diversity. Opportunity entrepreneurship and creative entrepreneurship, which Prof. Dr. Serkan Bayraktaroğlu mentioned as two basic types of entrepreneurships in his work titled Entrepreneurship Lecture Notes (Bayraktaroğlu, 2025) was taken as reference. In support of this, in a study where entrepreneurship types were defined according to different categories, creative entrepreneurship and opportunity entrepreneurship were considered together as a kind of basic group (Demirdöğmez, 2021).

Before examining opportunity entrepreneurship, it is necessary to look at the brief definition of the word ‘opportunity’ in this field. The set of ideas, beliefs and activities that allow the development of future products despite the existing market has been called opportunity (Bekmezci, 2017). In a study conducted on students, where it was stated that entrepreneurs should recognize and evaluate opportunities, it was stated that entrepreneurship begins with a business idea and that entrepreneurs aim to create value rather than material gain (Abacı, 2022). Opportunity is the most effective factor that stimulates entrepreneurial activity. It includes creativity, alertness, pragmatism, responsiveness to market sentiment, and investment skills (Bratu et al., 2009). Opportunity entrepreneurship, which is a type of entrepreneurship that includes perceiving and evaluating market opportunities and accepts an approach based on foresight and intuition, is a type of investment activity (Kalfaoğlu and Öge, 2018). In this context, when we associate opportunity entrepreneurship in agriculture with senior students of the faculty of agriculture, it is expected that they will tend towards opportunity entrepreneurship and be able to take innovative and creative actions by foreseeing products and services in quality and quantity that will solve the supply and demand problems brought about by fluctuations and crises in the agricultural market. As opportunity entrepreneurship is encouraged, economic recovery will increase (Acs et al., 2008). It is opportunity entrepreneurship that drives dynamic and sustainable economic development (Cervelló-Royo et al., 2020). Opportunity entrepreneurship is defined as a type of entrepreneurship that identifies good business opportunities and has a strong connection with growing entrepreneurial firms which are expected to create high employment (Fuentelsaz et al., 2019). Opportunity entrepreneurship refers to the situation where the individual turns to the innovative businesses of the future instead of the known individual businesses of today. It has been observed that when opportunity entrepreneurship are given space in unequal developing economies, such countries tend to adopt rational growth policies, encourage initiatives that are beneficial for employment creation and development, and ultimately aim to reduce inequalities (Cervelló-Royo et al., 2020). Another important issue in terms of inequalities is gender inequality. As gender equality approaches full equality, the population of female entrepreneurs who have the chance to use entrepreneurial skills will increase, and this will reflect the equality and homogeneity of opportunity entrepreneurship (Petraakis, 2012).

Entrepreneurs with high creativity skills who can see opportunities in gender equality environment have a strong entrepreneurial tendency. Creativity is a valuable inspirational ability (Parmer et al., 2023). The business establishment activity of a creative entrepreneur who is a talent investor in the creative industry which is an innovative tool that creates value and

helps development for the welfare of the country can be defined as creative entrepreneurship (Bujor and Avesilcai, 2014). Creative industries were made by clustering knowledge, technology, understanding and finance. This key sector of exports, employment and development is an important part of the knowledge economy (Küttim et al., 2011). Agriculture, which by its historical nature requires creativity, skills and talents, has the potential to create wealth and new needs through patents from innovation today, is also a creative industry. Fostering creative entrepreneurship becomes crucial for ensuring sustainable development and long-term success via creative industries. Creative entrepreneurs offer new processes and solutions to business life and society with creative strategies (Xiumiao and Suacamram, 2021). Creative entrepreneurship is not only the actions of entrepreneurs who use strategic opportunities to provide market advantage to the business, but also an activity that provides societal benefits. Creative entrepreneurship has been considered as a common value at the center of innovation, productivity growth, competitiveness, economic growth and employment, which are five of the modern elements of country development. Creative entrepreneurship, which is the result of the integration of creative and aesthetic sensitivity, business acumen and innovative understanding, is the locomotive of the economic recovery phase, especially for regional equal prosperity (Collins and Murtagh, 2024). Creative entrepreneurship, supported by the European Union through various programs and funds such as Horizon 2020, Erasmus +, INTERREG, is accepted by the European Commission as a tool that enables young people to develop skills in the process of learning entrepreneurship (Rudenko et al., 2022). There is an organic relationship between creativity and entrepreneurship. In the process of becoming an entrepreneur, an individual must be creative in order to discover and evaluate new opportunities within the framework of awareness and perception. A study that states that creativity is seen as an essential element of entrepreneurship reflects the idea that creativity must be a characteristic in order to find and evaluate opportunities in an entrepreneurial atmosphere (Anjum et al., 2021). The same study said that creativity emerges with initiative and high risk. It has been stated that creative individuals are more prone to entrepreneurship (Guerrero et al., 2020). In terms of the relationship between creativity and intention, a sample study indicated that initial creativity had a very positive effect on the entrepreneurial intentions of business owners (Basu and Virick, 2008). A positive link was found between entrepreneurial intention and creativity (Hamidi et al., 2008). As the first country to declare creative businesses as a strategic factor for development within the scope of the strategy of promoting creative entrepreneurship, which is one of the main objectives of the executive, England is gaining young people with creative minds as critical actors of the development of the UK economy in a kind of value hunting within

and outside the UK (Rudenko et al., 2022). At this point it was stated that “the perception of education has a vital role in increasing intention and creativity” (Anjum et al., 2021). These examples prove how important two valuable elements, creative entrepreneurship and youth, are for the transformation of developing countries like ours. As can be understood from these scientific findings, the educational role of universities on entrepreneurship and scientific research on creative entrepreneurship which is one of the basic types of entrepreneurship focused on new graduated young people who is everything for the economy as human resources, particularly in the agricultural major, is of great importance. Young people must be the main engines of the creative agricultural economy.

In light of the benefits highlighted, it appears that there are some research gaps in the field of education, which underlies entrepreneurship research. This study, as a research topic expected to contribute to the literature, specifically with the expectation of contributing to the agricultural industry, investigated the entrepreneurial intentions of senior agricultural faculty students taking entrepreneurship courses and their tendencies to the primary types of entrepreneurship with these intentions tend to pursue in the perspective of gender.

Material and Method

This research, which includes dependent and independent variables, used an online survey as the data collection tool. Quantitative research methods requiring numerical and statistical analysis were employed. Non-experimental descriptive and correlational designs were employed as research designs. Considering the importance of agriculture due to various strategic reasons and the developments related to entrepreneurship in the education and industry of this field, this research has been prepared for the senior students of the faculty of agriculture. The general universe of the research is the students who are in the graduation phase at the Faculties of Agriculture in Türkiye. However, due to the level of the research and the difficulties and limitations of reaching the general universe, senior students at the Faculty of Agriculture in Ondokuz Mayıs University was determined as the research universe of this study. The reasons for choosing the Faculty of Agriculture of Ondokuz Mayıs University as the field of research universe are both the inclusion of innovative courses such as the course of entrepreneurship in agriculture into the education system and the individual entrepreneurial activities and success stories of recently graduated students and current students. Therefore, the Faculty of Agriculture is an important study universe in itself. Complete census of this research is 169.

Questions regarding entrepreneurial intention and tendency to two basic types of entrepreneurship used within the scope of this research are included in the demographic part of

the questionnaire used in the master's thesis of Umut Ahmet Seyrek (Seyrek, 2025), the first author of this research. One question is "Which type of entrepreneurship do you see yourself closer to?". The two entrepreneurship types for this survey question were taken as reference from "Entrepreneurship Lecture Notes" (Bayraktaroğlu, 2025). Here, students are expected to choose one of the two basic groups of entrepreneurship, 'Opportunity' or 'Creative, or 'non of them' option. Other question is "Are you considering becoming an entrepreneur?". Students are expected to choose one option from "yes", "no", "undecided".

The all relevant analyzes were conducted at the the IBM SPSS26 program. Excel office program was also used for relevant calculations, graphs, tables and basic analysis. Descriptive statistic with explore analysis was used to summarize general characteristics of sampling data. Analyses were performed using chi-square goodness-of-fit and chi-square independence tests. In the statistical analysis of the data, a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Statement

The survey study, which included two questions regarding entrepreneurial intention and tendency towards basic entrepreneurship types used in this research, was approved by Ondokuz Mayıs University Social and Human Sciences Research Ethics Board (Annex 3) (Decision No: 2025-401).

Limitations

The research period of this research is limited to 2025. The participants are limited to senior students who took agricultural entrepreneurship class in agricultural faculty in OMU. The idea that our university may be a reference center representing the national or regional (like TR83) universe from the perspective of our country's agriculture has been effective in limiting this research to Faculty of Agriculture at Ondokuz Mayıs University. The research does not include any special criteria. There is no criterion for the participants not to be included in the research in any way. Except for the participant's free will, the researcher is not allowed to remove the participant after the research has started. There is no criterion in this regard. A methodological limitation is that, because all of the participants in this study received entrepreneurship training, no comparison was made between those who did and did not. Future studies could expand the research sample to include recent graduates (within a maximum of three years of graduation), graduate students, and doctoral students. If possible, a repeat study could be conducted with the same participants to investigate how their intentions and tendencies

have changed. This could provide data that will demonstrate the necessity of change and transformation in education, particularly for higher education institutions.

Research Hypotheses

H1: The distribution of students between the three thought states of intended, not intended and undecided about becoming an entrepreneur is not even.

H1a: Preferences regarding the idea of becoming an entrepreneur show statistically significant differences according to gender.

H2: The distribution of students among opportunistic entrepreneurial tendencies, creative entrepreneurial tendencies, and neither of these tendencies is unequal.

H2a: Tendencies to entrepreneurship types according to gender show statistically significant differences

H3: There is a significant relationship between the entrepreneurship type tendencies and gender of the participants who want to be entrepreneurs.

Findings and Discussion

Students participated in the survey independently of each other with their own free will. Each participant filled in all mandatory sections of the survey. The researchers assumed that each of the participating students sincerely responded to the survey with real information and real thoughts within a serious approach. The total sample size is 169. The number of male students is 99 (59% of the total number of participants) and the number of female students is 70 (41% of the total number of participants).

Figure 1. Distribution of students according to their intention to become entrepreneurs

Abacı (2022) indicated that “the individuals who received the entrepreneurship training are more inclined to the entrepreneurship than the others”. In the 2018-2019 academic year, in a research study had been conducted on a sample of 76 senior students who had been taking entrepreneurship course at the Faculty of Agriculture in our university, the participants were asked about their thoughts on becoming an entrepreneur. In the relevant study, 51.3% of the total sample answered 'yes' (Demir, 2018). In this entrepreneurship-themed study conducted seven years later after reference work in 2025, when the same question was asked to a sample size more than twice as large, the rate found was 36.7% (62 students) (Figure 1). Despite the scope of entrepreneurship education in agriculture has been developing, updating and expanding, it is important sign that there has been remarkable decrease in the intention of the new generation to become an entrepreneur over time. Another striking issue is the uncertainty in the minds of students who are about to graduate regarding the intention to become entrepreneurs. This may be an indicator of today's socio-economic uncertainty and the difficulty of adapting to unpredictable rapid changes. It is useful to define this in terms of gender.

H1: The distribution of students between the three thought states of intended, not intended and undecided about becoming an entrepreneur is not even.

Chi-Square Goodness of Fit Test was applied under the the non-parametric Legacy Dialogs in the SPSS26 program for testing this hypothesis. As a result of the test, it was determined that the students' thoughts about being an entrepreneur were not random or evenly distributed [$\chi^2(2) = 18.828, p < .001$]. Thus, H1 was accepted. Zero cells (0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is “56.3”. Result shows that there is a significance difference between observed and expected values. Undecided thought preferred by 76 students is high. That means the distribution of students according to preferences showed a significant difference. According to this result, it can be questioned the differences between preferences by gender.

Figure 2. Intention Distribution According to Gender

In the Figure 2, it was seen a possible inverse case between the two genders that will be examined in the test of the hypothesis revealing differences regarding the intention to be an entrepreneur. The percentages in the graph are the percentage distributions of the three answers within each group of women and men. Accordingly, 55.71% (39 female students) of 70 female students are indecisive in terms of the idea of being an entrepreneur. This indecisiveness is 37.37% (37 male students) among male students. The percentage distribution in terms of the intention to be an entrepreneur is 24.29% for women and 45.45% for men. According to the percentages, women appear indecisive and men appear intentioned.

H1a: Preferences regarding the idea of becoming an entrepreneur show statistically significant differences according to gender.

In the SPSS26 program, Chi-square test was applied. First of all, according to the test result, there is no missing value. A cross analysis result was obtained via comparing rates in gender by taking benefits from corrections in p value with Bonferroni option in the SPSS and also considering observed and expected values. Percentage and numerical distributions of students on preferences according to gender are exactly the values obtained in descriptive statistics. Since 0 cells (0%) have expected count less than 5, the interpretation was made according to the Pearson significance value. Pearson Chi-Square value is 8.255^a and Likelihood Ratio is “8.457”. Here Pearson Chi-square significance is “0.016”. Since P value is less than 0.05, answers according to gender show statistically significant difference. Thus, H1a is accepted. In a study where student entrepreneurial intention was considered as the dependent variable, a significant relationship was found between gender and intention (Mei et al., 2020).

The results of another study argued that gender influences students' decisions regarding entrepreneurship (Gajda, 2016).

Table 1. Intention and Gender Crosstabulation

			Gender	
			Male	Female
Do you consider becoming an entrepreneur?	No	Count	17 _a	14 _a
		Expected Count	18.2	12.8
		% within Gender	17.2%	20.0%
	Undecided	Count	37 _a	39 _b
		Expected Count	44.5	31.5
		% within Gender	37.4%	55.7%
	Yes	Count	45 _a	17 _b
		Expected Count	36.3	25.7
		% within Gender	45.5%	24.3%

As seen in Table 1, while 17% of the male participants do not want to be an entrepreneur, 20% of the female participants do not want to be an entrepreneur. There is no statistically significant difference between the two genders in terms of not intended to be an entrepreneur. However, the statistically significant difference in preferences according to gender, which confirms the hypothesis, is due to the significant differences observed in other two preferences which are indecision and intention to be an entrepreneur. Accordingly, the intention to be an entrepreneur is significantly higher in male students (45.5% of males) than in females, while the indecision rate (55.7% of females) is significantly higher in females.

Figure 3. Tendency Towards Entrepreneurship Type According to Gender

Participating students were asked which of the two basic types of entrepreneurship they were closer to. Of all the students in the sample, 89 students (%52.66) from total 169 student participants stated that they were prone to opportunistic entrepreneurship, 69 (%40.83) individuals within total stated that they were prone to creative entrepreneurship, and rest 11

individuals stated that they were prone to neither. Of these 11 individuals, 8 stated that they do not consider becoming an entrepreneur and 3 stated that they are undecided to be entrepreneur. In this context, there is a consistency among the 11 individuals about not have intention to be entrepreneur and no tendency to any type of entrepreneurship. ‘Figure 3’ shows a reverse tendency between women and men in terms of tendency to creative entrepreneurship and opportunity entrepreneurship. 55.71% of women stated that they were prone to creative entrepreneurship, while 61.62% of men stated that they were prone to opportunity entrepreneurship.

H2: The distribution of students among opportunistic entrepreneurial tendency, creative entrepreneurial tendency, and none of these tendencies is unequal.

The results of the Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit analysis indicated that the distribution was neither specific nor equal to the type of entrepreneurship [$\chi^2(2) = 58.272, p < .001$]. The minimum expected cell frequency was “56.3”. The result indicates a significant difference in the distribution of students according to their tendencies. H2 is accepted. Based on the absolute differences between the expected and observed values, preferred opportunistic entrepreneurial tendencies by 89 students (positive residual value 32.7) is over preferred creative entrepreneurial tendencies (positive residual value 12.7) by 69 students.

H2a: Tendencies towards entrepreneurship types according to gender show statistically significant differences.

In the descriptive statistics category of SPSS26 program, Chi-square test was applied. First, according to the test result, there is no missing value. By taking benefit the corrections in p value via Bonferroni method option in SPSS, ratios according to gender were compared. Observed and expected values were considered, and the cross-analysis result was interpreted. The percentage and numerical distributions of students regarding the tendency to entrepreneurship type according to gender are exactly the values obtained in descriptive statistics. The minimum expected value (4.56) is below 5 in only one comparison. In other words, since it is included in one of the 6 crossovers and less than 20% of all comparisons, the interpretation was made according to the Pearson significance value. 1 cells (16.7%) have expected count less than five. Pearson Chi-Square value is 11.031^a and Likelihood Ratio is “11.067”. Here, Pearson Chi-square significance is 0.004. Since the P value is less than 0.05, the tendency towards entrepreneurship type according to gender shows a statistically significant difference. H2a is accepted.

Table 2. Tendency to Type of Entrepreneurship and Gender Crosstabulation

			Gender	
			Male	Female
Type of Entrepreneurship	None of Them	Count	8 _a	3 _a
		Expected Count	6.4	4.6
		% within Gender	8.1%	4.3%
	Opportunity Entrepreneurship	Count	61 _a	28 _b
		Expected Count	52,1	36.9
		% within Gender	61.6%	40.0%
	Creative Entrepreneurship	Count	30 _a	39 _b
		Expected Count	40.4	28.6
		% within Gender	30.3%	55.7%

As seen in Table 2, there is statistically significant difference in terms of tendency to entrepreneurship type according to gender, which confirms the hypothesis. Accordingly, women see themselves closer to creative entrepreneurship and men to opportunity entrepreneurship. In other words, there is a non-random, systematic relationship between gender and tendency to entrepreneurship type. The high propensity of women in this field can be explained by the following reasons: Women can express themselves more freely in areas where they focus on creativity and innovation. In contrast to the barriers experienced in traditional entrepreneurship areas due to social norms, creative entrepreneurship is seen as a more open and supportive area. Women have higher intrinsic motivation, originality, and tendencies to create social value. On the other hand, a larger portion of male students were more hesitant to turn to creative entrepreneurship. This may suggest that men may tend to focus more on risk, profit, and competition elements in their perception of entrepreneurship. In a paper, It has been demonstrated that there is an interaction between gender and creativity, with a stronger relationship between women's intentions and creativity (Smith et al., 2016). In this context, similar conclusions were made to our current study, furthermore, it was suggested that, "in addition to incorporating creativity exercises into entrepreneurship curricula, programs should be developed and adapted to foster women's entrepreneurial intentions" (Smith et al., 2016). A study using a large sample including data of 17 countries obtained from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor comprising 2009 and 2014 found that gender influences opportunity-driven entrepreneurship and men are more opportunity-driven than women (Nasiri and Hamelin, 2018).

H3: There is a significant relationship between the tendency to entrepreneurship type and gender of the participants who want to be entrepreneurs.

To test this hypothesis, a total of 62 students who intended to become entrepreneurs were subjected to relevant statistical analysis. A striking point is that among students who intend to

become entrepreneurs, there are clearly no individuals who are undecided about their predisposition to the two main types of entrepreneurship. In the descriptive statistics category of SPSS26 program, Chi-square test was applied. Adjust p values (Bonferroni method) to compare column proportions was choiced under z test section. First, according to the test result, there is no missing value. Observed and expected values were considered, and the cross-analysis result was interpreted. The results obtained by testing this hypothesis support other hypothesis tests. The aim here is to clearly demonstrate the difference between females and males who are intended to be entrepreneur. The minimum expected value (7.4) is above 5. Since 0 cells (0%) have expected count less than 5 among 4 crossovers, the interpretation was made according to the Pearson significance value. Pearson Chi-Square value is 4.265^a and Likelihood Ratio is “4.267”. Here, Pearson Chi-square significance is “0.039”. Since the P value is less than 0.05, the tendency to entrepreneurship type according to gender among students who intend to become entrepreneurs shows a statistically significant difference. H3 is accepted.

Table 3. Entrepreneurship Type and Gender Crosstabulation

			Gender	
			Male	Female
Type of Entrepreneurship	Opportunity Entrepreneurship	Count	29 ^a	6 ^b
		Expected Count	25.4	9.6
		% within Gender	64.4%	35.3%
	Creative Entrepreneurship	Count	16 ^a	11 ^b
		Expected Count	19.6	7.4
		% within Gender	35.6%	64.7%

As seen in Table 3, there is statistically significant difference in terms of tendency to entrepreneurship type according to gender among students who want to be entrepreneurs, which confirms the hypothesis. Accordingly, %65 of women see themselves closer to creative entrepreneurship and %64 of men to opportunity entrepreneurship. Gender has a significant, moderataly high degree of influence on the predisposition of senior students who intend to become entrepreneurs to the basic entrepreneurial type.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examines the entrepreneurial intentions of senior agricultural students in relation to gender, revealing clear findings regarding how these intersect with predispositions toward two primary types of entrepreneurship. The results offer a micro-scale perspective on entrepreneurship and gender-based differences in the future of the agricultural sector and the orientation of new human resources to agriculture. Before starting the research, all the hypotheses formulated as a result of the expectations that the distribution of students according

to their desire to become entrepreneurs (willing, unwilling, and undecided), the tendency distribution towards two of the basic types of entrepreneurship, the effect of gender on both the preference for the idea of becoming an entrepreneur and the tendency towards the type of entrepreneurship, and especially the tendency of students who want to become entrepreneurs towards the two types of entrepreneurship according to their gender, would be statistically significant, were accepted as expected as a result of the statistical analyses. The statistically significant findings are noteworthy. When the sample is considered as a whole, it is seen that the students are undecided and opportunity-prone about entrepreneurship. When we evaluate the situation from a gender perspective, female students are generally ambivalent about becoming an entrepreneur, but female students who intend to become entrepreneurs (65%) are significantly more inclined to creative entrepreneurship. Male students, on the other hand, are generally more intended to be entrepreneurs, and male students who disposed to become entrepreneurs (64%) see themselves as significantly more inclined to opportunity entrepreneurship. When we evaluated differences without considering intention case, 56% of women are creative entrepreneurship and 62% of men are opportunity entrepreneurship-prone. It was seen that these values are proportionally slightly higher in those with entrepreneurial intentions. Taken together, these findings suggest that gender plays a significant role in determining entrepreneurial intentions and tendency to entrepreneurship types within the agricultural discipline. The findings of this study offer important insights into the development of educational practices, sectoral and institutional strategies, and related policies that consider gender differences in the integration of agricultural students into the profession and the future within the context of entrepreneurial orientation. At the core of entrepreneurship education, the concepts of creativity and opportunity should be integrated into relevant curricula, taking gender diversity into account and aligning with the needs and developments in agriculture. Transforming students into entrepreneurial mindsets that are more innovative, creative, and capable of opportunity-focused thinking and development is emerging as a critical research topic for the future of agriculture.

The gender-based differences revealed in the study indicate the need for more sophisticated support mechanisms. Female students demonstrated both a tendency toward creative entrepreneurship and higher levels of entrepreneurial indecision. This study serves as a resource for further studies exploring the reasons behind female students' indecision and creative tendencies. The results suggest that mentoring and guidance programs can be provided within university incubation centers to support female students' potential in entrepreneurship, a

driving force in today's economy, in decision-making processes. Given that female students are significantly more likely to engage in creative entrepreneurship, universities and incubators should establish dedicated spaces or platforms that promote creative industries, social innovation, and arts-based entrepreneurship, both within and outside of agriculture. These avenues can help capitalize on the originality exhibited by female students while also mitigating the impact of traditional entrepreneurial barriers shaped by societal norms.

Male students, who are more likely to engage in opportunity entrepreneurship, can take advantage of elective courses outside the traditional curriculum. Topics such as risk management, financial planning, and strategic opportunity recognition can support their entrepreneurial profiles. Programs designed with contextual factors in mind can create more inclusive entrepreneurial ecosystems.

Agricultural faculties and industry stakeholders can be expected to collaborate on the types of entrepreneurship in which students will play a role in the sustainability of modern agriculture and agricultural business development. This study contributes to the relevant literature and relevant stakeholders, particularly in the field of agriculture, within the framework of the roles and relationships of gender on entrepreneurial intention and tendency to basic types of entrepreneurship.

Thanks

We would like to thank the esteemed students for their sincere and serious contributions to a scientific study.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Contribution Rate Statement

Seyrek U.A. and Demiryürek K. contributed conceptualization. Seyrek U.A. and Abacı N.İ. conducted data collection, formal analysis, and methodology. Seyrek U.A. wrote original draft. Seyrek U.A., Demiryürek K. and Abacı N.İ. wrote review and editing.

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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